

1 **Papillomavirus oncogene expression in vitro.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells with engineered over-expression of papillomavirus oncogenes E6
7 and E7 for discovery of HPV oncogene regulated targets and pathways. We report here one such target,
8 silenced by the papillomavirus type 16 E6 and E7 oncogenes, the glycolipid transfer protein *GLTP*.

9 Citations

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